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Instructional Coaching on Physical Education Teachers' Efficacy

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study is to critically examine the level of Instructional Coaching on Physical Education Teachers' Efficacy and provide a program planned for the development of skills and talents of Physical Education teachers through a coaching program based on the result of this study. This is to improve the teachers' efficacy among PE teachers through instructional coaching in this domain, assessment and feedback, classroom management, instructional strategies, and student engagement. The respondents of the study were 60 public secondary school MAPEH teachers teaching MAPEH subjects in the Division of Cotabato City and Maguindanao del Sur using complete enumeration. The analysis shows that gender, monthly income, and position are associated with certain dimensions of teacher efficacy. The correlation analysis between instructional coaching and teachers' efficacy is not statistically significant correlations between the level of instructional coaching (either planning or observations and feedback) and the teacher's efficacy in various dimensions of teaching. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. Generally, the result of this suggests that instructional coaching must be implemented consistently to meet the effectiveness of this program to attain the teachers' efficacy among physical education teachers.

Keywords: *coaching, instructional and teachers' efficacy*

Introduction

Instructional coaching is one of the best ways to improve teaching performance and develop the self-efficacy of a teacher. As a professional development tool, instructional coaching has been widely implemented across Malaysia by focusing on providing pedagogical support to teachers and acting to bridge the gap between low-performing and high-performing schools (Malaysian Education Ministry, 2013).

Instructional coaching is a way of embedding professional learning opportunities into the day-to-day work of teachers. Instructional coaches can support the development of teacher knowledge, skills, motivation, and collaboration (Knight & Aguilar, 2013). Their work can increase teacher efficacy and agency in the coachee's ability to promote students' learning (Kraft et al., 2018) and increase teacher retention rates, particularly in urban settings (De Jong & Campoli, 2018).

Teacher efficacy is constructed upon the belief in one's ability to arrange, organize, implement, and execute instruction successfully (Tschannen-Moran et al., 1998). Effects of teacher efficacy contribute to capacity building within an individual, which leads to increased confidence in the ability to teach and affect student learning Bandura, A. The combination of self-perception and individual conviction in one's capability to administer sound lessons results in successful instructional practices (Marzano & Simms, 2014).

To contribute to the knowledge base of educators, policymakers, teacher educators, and administrators who are engaged in the process of teacher education and development, numerous studies have been done on instructional coaching and teachers' efficacy as part of the professional development of teachers. Research indicates that instructional coaching has a positive impact on teachers' efficacy (Simpson, 2020). This coaching assisted in locating resources for teachers to use in their classrooms, giving constructive feedback, and encouraging teachers to be reflective. Instructional coaches have a deep knowledge of instructional practices, enabling them to offer more options to teachers who partner with them to meet students' needs (Knight, 2019).

In my experience, instructional coaching has been beneficial to my teaching strategies, particularly when I get feedback from my mentors. I was excited to implement what I had read and heard in their remarks during my next teaching session. We received great coaching throughout the epidemic on how to use technology to teach physical education and how to be creative in our teaching methods. Another was my co-teacher, who is an expert in basketball sports officiating, and my observer, who taught me how to properly apply basketball sports officiating in every classroom I saw. I suppose I've made progress in this direction. Since then, I've gained the confidence to manage my basketball lessons by myself.

In my perception, I believe that the best comments that you receive are those things that will reinforce your teaching quality because they will have a good impact on the student's outcome. Suggestions and feedback have one objective, which is assessing the quality of education that you give to the learners and developing our competencies. Sweeney and Mausbach (2018) stated, "Coaching is designed to increase efficacy because it is built on the foundation of helping the teachers reach their goals for student learning" while "Teaching efficacy" describes a teacher's belief in their ability to enhance the learning outcomes of students.

Furthermore, this study intends to explore how junior high school PE teachers perceive the effects of an instructional coaching program on their pedagogical strategies that develop the teachers' efficacy in various teaching dimensions like assessment and feedback, classroom management, student engagement, and instructional strategies. Knight (2016) stated that the purpose of instructional

coaching programs is connected to the larger concept of system-wide, or organizational, change. The instructional coach position in K–12 schools grew out of a need to change educational practices that were no longer meeting the needs of students. Instructional coaching programs were designed as an intervention: by helping teachers improve the quality of their instruction, students would increase their academic performance and schools would meet state and federal reform mandates (Tierney, 2020).

Teachers with high self-efficacy levels have the professional competence that is essential to the teaching profession, have classroom management, education planning, implementation, and assessment knowledge and skills, and are equipped with the skills required to motivate students to engage in their class and their overall education. One needs to be mindful that developing self-efficacy enables the person to have the identifiable role of having the right intentions. Likewise, the intention has an equally vital role in the physical education of the students to achieve the desired purpose of making them creative intellectual thinkers (Novitasari et al., 2021).

In this study, the researcher wants to justify how instructional coaching can help develop teachers' efficacy among PE teachers, the instructional coaching processes availed by the teachers can help them improve their teaching strategies and become skillful in teaching physical education. Another reason to pursue this study is to emphasize the importance of the implementation of coaching. This can be an alternative or an intervention to professional development that might have positive effects on teachers' efficacy and some dimensions of teaching. This approach encourages learning, growth, and teamwork all at the same time. For these reasons, teachers are expected to achieve the goal of the DepEd to produce globally skilled and competitive graduates (Elanga, 2017).

To meet the growing needs of diverse learners, it is paramount that teachers continually reflect upon their craft so that they can change what is not working and fine-tune what is (Knight et al., 2016). District leaders can support the advancement and growth of teacher's pedagogical strategies by providing an instructional coach at the site or district level (Knight et al., 2016). In addition, with the support of an instructional coach, the aim is to improve students' academic performance and thereby meet state and federal reform mandates (Tierney, 2020).

As stipulated in DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015 (Guidelines on the Establishment and Implementation of RPMS in DepEd), RPMS is a systemic mechanism to manage, monitor, and measure performance, and identify human resource and organizational development needs to enable continuous work improvement and individual growth. This is implemented through performance monitoring and coaching from the school administration. Implementing instructional coaching is a strategy to support teachers in these areas (Marzano & Simms, 2014) and has been found to significantly increase teacher retention rates, especially in urban settings (De Jong & Campoli, 2018).

The Department of Education (DepEd) underscored anew the importance of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) that is aligned with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) in ensuring the delivery of quality, accessible, relevant, and liberating basic education in the country. The current trends in education show that 'effective coaching and mentoring programs are regarded as a highly effective method of assisting individuals in increasing their self-direction, self-esteem, efficacy, and accomplishments through communication (Ellinger, Hamlin, & Beattie, 2016).

To give significance to these requirements, school teachers face a new and difficult challenge, since they are required to fulfill stricter criteria and maintain their teaching standards at a higher level than in previous years. For this reason, they must implement new strategies that can help them strengthen the quality of the teaching-learning process in their classes. To respond to the demands of the 21st century, as well as to manage the new standards of education restructuring, Philippine teachers, hence, need to keep refining their performance, as well as their efficacy. Today's teachers must teach content and motivate students to attend to learning in an environment dominated by external influences. In addition, teachers need to be able to develop new skills, or modify existing ones, to ensure learner needs are met. Particularly when students are vastly different from their teachers socially, culturally, and economically; and who are used to learning through technology (Teemant, 2014).

This study wants to determine factors that can affect the teachers' efficacy through instructional coaching and the level of teacher efficacy in classroom management, student engagement, instructional strategies, and assessment and feedback in teaching physical education. The background information included the teachers' age, gender, civil status, length of service, education level, position, and monthly income in which they were working which might have a significant positive effect on their decisions on the utilization of instructional coaching as a way to the development of physical education teacher's efficacy.

Research Questions

This study determined the level of instructional coaching and its effects on teacher efficacy of the Physical Education teachers of BARRM, School Year 2022-2023 as the basis for the Instructional Coaching Enhancement Program. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 gender;
 - 1.3 educational attainment;
 - 1.4 length of service;

- 1.5 civil status;
- 1.6 monthly income; and
- 1.7 position?
2. What is the level of instructional coaching to PE teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1 planning; and
 - 2.2 observations and feedback?
- 3 What is the level of teachers' efficacy of P.E. teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1 assessment and feedback;
 - 3.2 classroom management;
 - 3.3 instructional strategies; and
 - 3.4 students engagements?
4. Is there a significant relationship between
 - 4.1 teachers' demographic profile and teachers' efficacy;
 - 4.2 teachers demographic profile and instructional coaching; and
 - 4.3 level of instructional coaching and teacher's efficacy?
5. Based on the findings, what enhanced Instructional Coaching Program can be designed?

Methodology

This section deals with the discussion of the method to be used, the source of data, gathering instruments, sampling techniques of the study, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

In this study, quantitative research was used, according to Creswell (2014), quantitative research is “a means for testing objective theories by examining the relationship among variables. These variables, in turn, can be measured, typically on instruments, so that numbered data can be analyzed using statistical procedures”. Some strategies of inquiry that are mainly associated with quantitative research are the survey method and descriptive -survey method used to measure the Level of Instructional Coaching to Physical Education Teachers' Efficacy. A descriptive study is designed to describe the distribution of one or more variables without regard to any causal or other hypotheses (Agarwal et al., 2019).

This study employed a descriptive-correlational design. According to Panda (2022), descriptive correlational design is used in research studies that provide static pictures of situations and establish the relationship between different variables

In this study, the researcher explored the relationship between Instructional coaching and Teacher Efficacy of Physical Education Teachers to demographic profiles such as Age, Gender, Educational Attainment, Length of Service, Civil Status, Monthly Income, Status of Employment, and Position. Furthermore, the level of instructional coaching and the teacher's efficacy were also assessed.

Participants

The respondents of this study were the 60 Junior High School Physical Education Teachers. They are from two division schools of the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in the Muslim Mindanao Region.

The respondents of the study were public secondary school teachers teaching MAPEH subjects and also graduates of BSEd MAPEH in the Division of Cotabato City and Maguindanao del Sur division. Presently, the complete enumeration of 60 MAPEH teachers was selected. The researcher was provided implied consent to the perspective respondents to ensure that they voluntarily submit themselves to participate in the study. They were informed that they can freely withdraw as soon as they wish.

Instruments

The research was patterned after the content of the survey questionnaire.

The survey questionnaire was composed of two major parts. The first part was composed of a level of instructional coaching as a professional development intervention. The second part was composed of statements on the level of the effect of instructional coaching on teachers' efficacy and performance of PE teachers in the BARMM Region.

Part I covered the statements that briefly described the level of instructional coaching using the performance indicators following the scale 5-Strongly Agree 4- Agree 3-Nither Agree or Disagree 2-Disagree 1-Strongly Disagree.

Part II The researcher adopted the Teacher Self-efficacy Scale (TSES) developed by Tschannen-Moran and Hoy (2001). It was considered to be one of the best instruments to gauge teacher self-efficacy because it is a standardized instrument and has been used in many different researches of the same nature. There were 24 questions in the questionnaire which are further divided into three sub-scales: classroom management (8 questions), instructional strategies (8 questions), and student engagement (8 questions) to judge teacher self-efficacy. It has 9 9-point Likert scale labeled with the notations: nothing, very little, some influence, quite a bit, and a great

deal. For the ease of the participants, the instrument was later converted into a 5-point Likert scale from nothing (1) to a great deal (5). The overall reliability (Cronbach Alpha) of the instrument was .94

Procedure

Pre-Data Gathering. The researcher sent a transmittal letter to the dean and president of the Graduate School of Education asking for authorization to administer the survey. The researcher reviewed the protocol and met with a study representative before beginning the study to fill out an informed consent form that had been approved by the University of Visayas' Institutional Review Board. The researcher requested permission to conduct the study and obtain information on the total number of teachers in MAPEH in a letter to the superintendents of the school divisions of the Cotabato City and Maguindanao Del Sur divisions. In addition, the researcher sent a letter to the MAPEH Teachers who participated in the study and the school principal requesting their agreement for the survey. The researcher contacted all of the teachers who indicated interest in taking part in enhancing this study and the application of behavior management strategies.

Actual Data Gathering. The questionnaire was distributed last September 04, 2023, at the schools of Cotabato City Division from 8 am to 11:30 am until 1:00 pm to 4:00 pm. On September 11, 2023, the questionnaire was distributed to the Maguindanao Del Sur Division. On the day of the data gathering, the researchers interviewed the respondents to gather opinions about problems encountered in the implementation of Instructional Coaching. The researcher once again explained the purpose and mechanics of the survey so that the respondents would have an idea about the said survey. Hence, the data on the performance evaluation of the respondents were taken through the answered standardized questionnaire including the qualitative data. After five days the researcher collected the questionnaire.

Post - Data Gathering. The data gathered were collected, tallied, tabulated, and statistically treated using the Pearson– Test used for testing significant relationships between categorical variables. The Test of Independence assesses whether an association exists between the two variables by comparing the observed pattern of responses in the cells to the pattern that would be expected if the variables were truly independent of each other.

Statistical Analysis

The mean and standard deviation were used in instructional coaching and the PE teacher's efficacy. Mean is the measure of central tendency. Singh (2007) claims that the basic way to describe a particular phenomenon is to employ descriptive statistical analysis which normally pertains to profile. The mean is one of the measures of central location that describes the characteristics of a person or group of persons phenomena. It is the most reliable measure of central tendency. The standard deviation quantifies the degree of dispersion of the data concerning the mean. Data with a low standard deviation, or small standard deviation, are closely grouped around the mean, whereas data with a big standard deviation, or large standard deviation, are widely dispersed.

Pearson's correlation coefficient is the test statistics used to quantify the association, or statistical link, between two continuous variables. Because it is based on the method of covariance, it is regarded as the best way to measure the relationship between variables of interest. It provides details on the direction of the relationship as well as the strength of the association, or correlation.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher followed the standards mandated by the school as the ethical guidelines for conducting the research. Primarily, compliance with the protocols of research ethical considerations will be observed in this paper. Then the voluntary consent of participants having been informed of their rights to continue or withdraw their participation in the study without any prejudice to them will be asked. They were likewise assured that the data gathered from them would be used solely for research and that utmost secrecy be observed in the treatment and use of all data.

The researcher will ensure methodological cohesions by being a responsive investigator through acquiring adequate samples and attending to rational ethics to assure credibility. The study will use an adequate number of respondents which conforms with the inclusion criteria described in the respondents' section. Supporting the findings with the literature and previous studies helped to establish the reliability of the data gathered

The following are the points that were considered in this study to ensure that human rights were protected, that the benefits outweigh the risks if there are any, that content, comprehension, and documentation implied consent were observed, authorization to access private information was prepared before the research data gathering, confidentiality procedures, debriefing, communications and referrals, and conflict of interest was taken into consideration too.

Results

This section indicates the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered in this study. The data were obtained from the standardized questionnaire given on the assessment of the Instructional Coaching on Physical Education Teachers' Efficacy.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents N=60

Age	Frequency	Percentage
23-28	20	33.33
29-34	22	36.66
35-40	9	15
41-46	7	11.66
47 above	2	3.33
Gender		
Male	40	66.66
Female	20	33.33
Educational attainment		
Degree holder	42	70
Master's degree	16	26.66
Doctoral Degree	1	1.66
Others	0	0
Length of service		
1-5	32	53.33
6-10	15	25
11-15	10	16.66
16-20	2	3.33
21 above	1	1.66
Civil status		
Single	22	36.7
Married	36	60.0
Separated	1	1.7
Widow	1	1.7
Monthly Income		
27,000-30,587	42	70
30,588-34,175	16	26.67
34,176-37,763	0	0
37,764-41,351	1	1.66
41,352 above	1	1.67
Position		
Teacher I	40	66.7
Teacher II	1	1.7
Teacher III	17	28.3
Master Teacher I	2	3.3
Master Teacher II		
Master Teacher III		

Table 2. Instructional Coaching to PE Teachers in terms of Planning

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. Instructional leaders at my school effectively assist me in analyzing student work and performance data.	4.33	.752	Strongly Agree
2. My instructional leaders are available to support me with instructional planning.	4.40	.669	Strongly Agree
3. I receive quality support throughout the instructional planning process.	4.28	.739	Strongly Agree
4. My instructional plans are consistently reviewed, and feedback is given promptly.	4.43	.621	Strongly Agree
5. I receive meaningful feedback on my instruction plans.	4.40	.669	Strongly Agree
Overall mean	4.37	.581	Strongly Agree

Note: N=60; 1.00-1.80 – Strongly Disagree; 1.81-2.60- Disagree; 2.61-3.40 – Neither agree or Disagree; 3.41-4.20; Agree; 4.21-5:00- Strongly Agree

Table 3. Instructional Coaching to PE Teachers in terms of Observations and Feedback

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. I am observed frequently and receive feedback consistently.	4.27	.634	Strongly Agree
2. The feedback I receive from leaders at my school helps positively impact student achievement.	4.33	.601	Strongly Agree
3. I participate in development meetings and sessions that deepen my content knowledge or develop new skills that I can immediately apply in my classroom.	4.38	.640	Strongly Agree
4. My instructional coach responds to my requests for assistance promptly.	4.52	.567	Strongly Agree
5. I practice classroom management techniques and lesson execution with other teachers and leaders at my school.	4.53	.623	Strongly Agree

6. My coach provides me with exemplar videos or live models to demonstrate effective teaching methods.	4.25	.704	Strongly Agree
7. My coach seeks out resources to help meet my needs.	4.32	.596	Strongly Agree
8. I regularly discuss feedback about my teaching with an instructional leader or coach at my school.	4.40	.558	Strongly Agree
9. My instructional coach effectively assists me with strategies to better engage my students in their learning.	4.35	.515	Strongly Agree
10. After observations, I receive feedback and action steps aligned to my development.	4.37	.610	Strongly Agree
11. After observations, I receive support on how to implement any feedback and/or action steps.	4.23	.745	Strongly Agree
12. An instructional leader follows up to ensure I am implementing feedback and action steps.	4.37	.610	Strongly Agree
13. My instructional leader is an effective listener.	4.27	.607	Strongly Agree
14. My instructional leader effectively engages team members & other faculty in reflecting upon their professional practices.	4.47	.536	Strongly Agree
15. I am satisfied with the overall development that my coach has provided.	4.42	.671	Strongly Agree
16. Instructional leaders at my school are effective in helping positively impact student achievement.	4.53	.503	Strongly Agree
Overall mean	4.48	.504	Strongly Agree

Note: N=60; 1.00-1.80 – Strongly Disagree; 1.81-2.60- Disagree;2.61-3.40 – Neither agree or Disagree; 3.41-4.20; Agree; 4.21-5:00- Strongly Agree

Table 4. Teachers' Efficacy of P.E. Teachers in terms of Assessment and Feedback

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. How much can you do to get through to the most difficult students?	4.03	.863	Quite a bit
2. How much can you do to help your students think critically?	4.03	.901	Quite a bit
3. How much can you do to control disruptive behavior in the classroom?	4.07	.841	Quite a bit
4. How much can you do to motivate students who show low interest in schoolwork?	4.18	.833	Quite a bit
5. I receive meaningful feedback on my instruction plans.	4.18	.833	Quite a bit
6. How much can you do to get students to believe they can do well in schoolwork?	4.23	.789	A Great Deal
Overall mean	4.12	.810	Quite a bit

Note: N=60; 1.00-1.80 – Strongly Disagree; 1.81-2.60- Disagree;2.61-3.40 – Neither agree or Disagree; 3.41-4.20; Agree; 4.21-5:00- Strongly Agree

Table 5. Teachers' Efficacy of P.E. Teachers in terms of Classroom Management

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. How much can you do to control disruptive behavior in the classroom?	3.92	.809	Quite a bit
2. I receive meaningful feedback on my instruction plans.	4.03	.780	Quite a bit
3. How well can you establish routines to keep activities running smoothly?	4.03	.663	Quite a bit
4. How much can you do to get children to follow classroom rules?	4.05	.891	Quite a bit
5. How much can you do to calm a student who is disruptive or noisy?	4.12	.804	Quite a bit
6. How well can you establish a classroom management system with each group of students?	4.12	.825	Quite a bit
7. How well can you keep a few problems students from ruining an entire lesson?	4.03	.863	Quite a bit
8. How well can you respond to defiant students?	4.07	.841	Quite a bit
Overall mean	4.04	.736	Quite a bit

Note: N=60; 1.00-1.80 – Strongly Disagree; 1.81-2.60- Disagree;2.61-3.40 – Neither agree or Disagree; 3.41-4.20; Agree; 4.21-5:00- Strongly Agree

Table 6. Teachers' Efficacy of P.E. Teachers in terms of Instructional Strategies

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. How well can you respond to difficult questions from your students?	3.97	.780	Quite a bit
2. How much can you gauge student comprehension of what you have taught?	4.12	.691	Quite a bit
3. To what extent can you craft good questions for your students?	4.13	.724	Quite a bit
4. How much can you do to adjust your lessons to the proper level for individual students?	4.17	.847	Quite a bit
5. How much can you use a variety of assessment strategies?	4.17	.763	Quite a bit
6. To what extent can you provide an alternative explanation or example when students are confused?	4.07	.841	Quite a bit
7. How well can you implement alternative strategies in your classroom?	4.18	.833	Quite a bit
8. How well can you provide appropriate challenges for very capable students?	4.23	.789	A Great Deal
Overall mean	4.12	.736	Quite a bit

Note: N=60; 1.00-1.80 – Strongly Disagree; 1.81-2.60- Disagree;2.61-3.40 – Neither agree or Disagree; 3.41-4.20; Agree; 4.21-5:00- Strongly Agree

Table 7. Teachers' Efficacy of P.E. Teachers in Terms of Student Engagements

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. How much can you do to get through to the most difficult students?	3.85	.899	Quite a bit
2. How much can you do to help your students think critically?	3.98	.854	Quite a bit
3. How much can you do to motivate students who show low interest in schoolwork?	4.08	.869	Quite a bit

4. How much can you do to get students to believe they can do well in schoolwork?	4.03	.843	Quite a bit
5. How much can you do to help your students value learning?	4.13	.724	Quite a bit
6. How much can you do to foster student creativity?	4.18	.748	Quite a bit
7. How much can you do to improve the understanding of a student who is failing?	4.13	.833	Quite a bit
8. How much can you assist families in helping their children do well in school?	4.18	.833	Quite a bit
Overall mean	4.07	.753	Quite a bit

Note: N=60; 1.00-1.80 – Strongly Disagree; 1.81-2.60- Disagree; 2.61-3.40 – Neither agree or Disagree; 3.41-4.20; Agree; 4.21-5.00- Strongly Agree

Table 8. Correlation Analysis Between Teachers’ Demographic Profile and Instructional Coaching

Demographic profile	Instructional Coaching					
	Planning		Observations and Feedback		Overall	
	r	Sig	r	Sig	r	Sig
Age	-.094	.473	-.068	.608	-.091	.488
Gender	-.074	.576	-.033	.805	-.062	.637
Educational attainment	.102	.436	.086	.511	.105	.425
Length of service	-.028	.832	-.095	.472	-.061	.645
Civil status	-.071	.591	.125	.340	.011	.933
Monthly Income	-.084	.525	-.061	.646	-.081	.538
Position	-.075	.569	-.029	.827	-.061	.642

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 9. Correlation analysis between Teachers’ demographic profile and teachers’ efficacy

Demographic profile	Teachers’ Efficacy									
	Students Engagement		Classroom Management		Instructional Strategies		Assessment and feedback		Overall	
	r	Sig	r	Sig	r	Sig	r	Sig	r	Sig
Age	.147	.263	.136	.301	.174	.183	.146	.266	.153	.244
Gender	.252	.052	.232	.075	.236	.070	.057	.057	.246	.059
Educational attainment	-.034	.797	-.045	.730	-.017	.897	-.034	.796	-.033	.801
Length of service	.064	.629	.061	.644	.092	.484	.089	.499	.078	.555
Civil status	.156	.234	.161	.220	.183	.163	.128	.329	.159	.226
Monthly Income	-.225	.083	-.258*	.046	-.204	.119	-.251	.053	-.238	.067
Position	-.258*	.046	-.288*	.026	-.262*	.043	-.314*	.015	-.285*	.027

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 10. Correlation analysis between Level of instructional coaching and teacher’s efficacy

Instructional Coaching	Teacher’s Efficacy									
	Assessment and feedback		Classroom Management		Instructional Strategies		Students Engagements		Overall	
	r	Sig	r	Sig	r	Sig	r	Sig	r	Sig
Planning	-.138	.293	-.116	.379	-.120	.362	-.041	.754	-.104	.429
Observations and Feedback	.035	.789	.040	.759	.050	.703	.063	.634	.048	.715

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Discussion

This presents the overall result of the study measuring the level of instructional coaching to Physical Education Teachers’ Efficacy.

This study set out to measure the efficacy of instructional coaching provided to physical education teachers. This includes the demographic composition of instructors' efficacy and instructional coaching (Aguilar, 2013). States that instructional coaches can foster the expansion of teachers' knowledge, abilities, zeal, and collaboration (De Jong & Campoli, 2018). approach can enhance teacher efficacy and action in the coachee's capacity to stimulate students' learning and raise teacher retention rates, mostly in urban settings.

Level of Demographic Profile Between Instructional Coaching

This study found that measuring between demographic profile and instructional coaching has no statistically significant relationship therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. The results of the study of Walsh, Ginger, and Akhavan (2020). Teachers with 15 or more years of experience show the lowest mean score in the overall perceived impact of instructional coaching. Novice teachers (0-3 years of service) perceived a significantly higher impact of instructional coaching on their efficacy in the classroom than veteran teachers (15+ years of service).

This implies that demographic factors do not appear allied with instructional coaching outcomes. This means that instructional coaching applies to all ages, genders, and civil-status teachers with higher positions, income, length of service, and educational attainment. Implementation of instructional coaching should be participated by faculty members despite their differences in all aspects. The result of this study is contrary to the study of Dien, Abang, and Ngban(2022) that the age of a teacher as an asset influences their job performance in terms of knowledge of subject matter, classroom management, instructional delivery, and disciplinary measures.

Shah and Udgaonkar (2018) posit that the more advanced a teacher is in age, the more he becomes experienced and knows where to tap the potential of the students and how to make them understand this worth. This factor seems to be controversial as it influences teachers' effectiveness because some scholars think that indeed teachers' gender influences teachers' effectiveness while others argue that it does not have any significant influence.

Correlation Analysis Between Teachers' Demographic Profile and Teachers' Efficacy.

The findings of the study revealed that gender, monthly income, and position have a significant relationship to teachers' efficacy. The result, however, agrees with the result obtained by th Odanga et al. (2015) that marital status had no statistically significant influence on teachers' self-efficacy.

Amalu (2021) opines that gender influences teachers' effectiveness in terms of instructional delivery, disciplinary measures, and communication skills with the reason given to be that female teachers are good orators when it has to do with the utilization of words and patience in organizing their classes. personality traits necessary to become an effective teacher compared to their male counterparts who may be well equipped and sophisticated in terms of knowledge of the subject matter but yet not sympathetic like the female.

The result of the finding also showed that female teachers have higher efficacy than their male counterparts. Gender differences in teacher efficacious have been recognized as a probable variable accounting for specific differences in teacher practice. had less access to opportunities leaving them with less capacity to advance than men. The possible reason for this finding can be found in the assertion made by Nejati et al. that female teachers are more attentive, accurate, and planned than male teachers and as a result, they usually attempt to have the best instruction.

That is, "they are typically complex to teach efficiently and efficacious as they can and not to bounce everything since they pay consideration to niceties". Moreover, the study exhibited that male and female teachers did not differ in terms of classroom management and student engagement. The insinuation is that both male and female teachers have similar efficiencies in classroom management and student engagement. This result therefore is consistent with the preceding conclusion of who conducted a study to examine the relationship between gender and subscales of self-efficacy of Iranian EFL teachers and reported that male and female teachers did not differ as far as classroom supervision was prioritized and concerned (Sarfo et al., 2015).

The findings indicate that self-efficacy was lower among teachers in higher positions and with greater monthly salaries. According to the results of a recent study, practiced teachers did not perceive instructional coaching as having a significant impact on the development of their pedagogical strategies since they did not collaborate much with instructional coaches at their workplace.

This denotes that teachers with higher positions and monthly incomes had lesser efficacy in their ability to teach since they were assigned to more administrative duties and fewer subjects. Teachers are concentrating on their administrative tasks. They were not prioritizing the needs of the teachers and instructional coaching was not sustained before the goal of the Department of Education. Similarly, findings showed that teachers' teaching experience negatively influenced teachers' self-efficacy in teaching practices (Dickson et al., 2019).

Correlation Analysis Between Level of Instructional Coaching and Teacher's Efficacy.

There are no statistically significant correlations between the level of instructional coaching (either planning or observations and feedback) and teacher's efficacy in various dimensions of teaching. This is connected somewhat to the outcomes of the work of Walsh et al. (2020). Coaching is most effective when coaches sense goals are well-defined and believe it enhances professional learning in a transformational way. This result was supported by the narrative report from the interview.

In a similar vein, coaching or mentoring is a one-on-one connection that supports the mentee's growth and learning (Hobson et al., 2015). Mentoring involves very intimate exchanges that take place in various settings and educational institutions, although the duties involved in mentoring cannot be strictly defined. However, effective mentorship in schools plays a critical role in improving both new teachers' performance as teachers and veteran teachers' learning abilities.

In this study, the result presented that instructional coaching is less effective because there are lots of obstacles in attaining the consistency of the program implementation. Here are the reasons concluded on the interview of some respondents; (1.) Limited interaction with the coach (2.) Consistency of Classroom Observation (3.) Time Constraints (4.) Consistency of coaching and mentoring (5.) Hands-on-support (6.) Constant Implementation and Collaboration (7.) Moral and Spiritual Support.

Limited Interaction with the Coach. This statement indicates that feedback assessments and feedback are very helpful in improving strategies and developing teaching performance. Providing feedback on a teacher's classroom practice encourages teachers to reflect and develop self-awareness about their practice and offers evidence of concrete teacher performance, their strengths, and areas of

improvement. However, as the respondents said, there is room for interaction with the coach and enough time to demonstrate some strategies.

Consistency of Classroom Observation. Respondents suggested frequent classroom observation was required, especially undertaken by headteachers and colleague teachers, and that effective modalities regarding classroom observation would be worked out. This indicates that it would be better if school leaders visit teachers in their classrooms to see how they teach and if the Daily Lesson Log they prepare is related to their strategies. It would be the best way to give suggestions and comments that are concise and accurate.

DepEd has restated the necessity to carry on the conduct of all ongoing class observations to help guarantee the conveyance of excellent basic education to all learners under its care. The DepEd recognizes that teachers play a crucial role in upgrading the quality of the teaching and learning process. Through classroom observation, teacher's performance can be improved through different parameters is vital in achieving quality education. Classroom observation was mandated in the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers-Results-Based Performance Management System (PPST-RPMS).

Time Constraints. For coaching to work, understanding how much time is needed to move practice is critical. In short, teachers aren't spending enough time engaging in activities related to coaching, so they aren't likely to make significant changes in their instructional practice. The New Teacher Center, which has an established track record of improving practice via coaching and mentoring, suggests teachers need 1.25–2.5 hours per week of support.

Sixteen respondents, Management techniques in the classroom and lesson execution are very helpful and taught by my coach. However, we need some time with the coach for further instructional coaching, I think the conversation is not enough to sustain the needs of the teachers in developing strategies specifically when teaching sports we need some time to sit with the coach like for example team teaching.

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The result shows that instructional coaching is helpful in teachers' development however majority of the respondents stated that they need more time to interact with the coach and consistent classroom observation must be implemented so that change will be sustained continuously and strategies of teaching will be reinforced. When coaches make themselves visible and available to teachers beyond their classrooms and in common school spaces, coaches' access to classrooms may be enhanced. This includes instances in which coaches are present with teachers and students outside at bus duty, in the teachers' lounge and school hallways and at various school activities. When coaches are visible and available to teachers in these diverse settings, this sends the message to teachers that the coach has a vested interest in the school community which strengthens coach-teacher trust and ultimately the coaches (Saclarides & Munson, 2022).

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This above finding indicates that instructional coaching develops classroom management effectively. Effective classroom management is substantial to all teachers. It requires all aspects of what is going on in the classroom. Not only does classroom management comprise how the teacher delivers the curriculum, but also how the learners interact with the teachers.

Consistency of Coaching and Mentoring. This is similar to Tanner et al. (2017). who stated that instructional coaching is a consistent practice to learn, reflect, and commit to change. The lack of commitment to consistency is discouraging for teachers and administrators. Consistency constraints occur when there is a lack of time and commitment to the process. Teachers feel supported when they receive actionable feedback and can implement it in their classrooms.

Seven respondents replied that professional development is my utmost goal with instructional coaching and development. However, it will not be achieved if coaching and mentoring are not sustained and lack of time because coaches are busy. After they finished commenting and giving feedback there is no action for further development.

Eleven respondents articulated that, the ultimate goal of instructional coaching and development is professional development as an alternative to traditional professional development. I believe that development must be more effective if it's done in the actual situation and if it is implemented efficiently. I suggest that the coach must apply mentoring and demonstration for teachers so that instructional coaching is completely applied after the classroom observation.

The lack of guidance and mentorship for teachers, hindrances the consistency of coaching and mentoring especially those in the early stages of their careers, has been a significant concern in the field of education (Renbarger & Davis, 2019). Tanjung et al. (2021) shed light on the significance of mentorship for mutual professional development in the field of education. Additionally, mentorship has

been identified as a significant component in the professional training of young lecturers, enabling their continuous development emphasize the importance (Shepitko et al., 2022). of mentorship in enhancing the skills and competencies of inexperienced educators within the academic setting.

In the context of evolving educational requirements in the 21st century, there is a growing need for teachers to continuously develop their skills to meet the demands of teaching students core competencies such as critical thinking, cross-cultural understanding, and ICT literacy. Studies have identified various effective methods for teacher professional development, including peer-mentoring, continual development, and the integration of ICT teaching Yue, X., (2019). Furthermore, the impact of teacher professional development on student outcomes has been explored in different settings. Research has shown a positive association between teacher evaluation and professional development, emphasizing the importance of feedback and support for educators to enhance their practices (Alwaely et al., 2023).

The findings supported by Bambrick-Santoyo (2012) pick up from Lemov's idea of high-leverage feedback and its value and emphasize deliverance in a timely, consistent manner. In Bambrick's observation and feedback model, the theory is that consistent dialogue and feedback directly inform teacher practices. The outlines the four keys to making a productive observation and feedback model realized: regular observation, the right high-leverage action steps, effective feedback, and accountability. This is a call to action and pushes systematic coordination within our nation's schoolhouses.

Hands-on Support, Moral and Spiritual Support. The majority of the respondents want to have hands-on coaching peer coaching can include a pair or a team of coaches co-planning a lesson or curriculum unit, problem-solving, analyzing videos of lessons or study groups, and leading action research.

Suriano et al. (2018) conducted a case study highlighting meaningful instructional coaching strategies teachers benefit from, including when they feel supported because it creates empowerment. When teachers have access to resources, they feel supported by those involved in the instructional coaching process. Support is a category that helps teachers and administrators improve their instructional practices.

Implication

The result of this study suggested that instructional coaching must be implemented consistently to meet the effectiveness of this program to attain the teachers' efficacy among physical education teachers. The training must be redesigned and enriched to modify the current education trends and needs to empower teachers with high self-efficacy beliefs and self-regulation of learning. Teachers' self-efficacy is a key driver of teacher performance and the training provided to teachers helps them to build positive self-efficacy. Physical Education Teachers want and need practical in-service training to make them better and skillful teachers and that improves student outcomes. With these teachers can make teaching more successive, effective, and efficient. The findings of this study found that instructional coaching has not been significantly correlated to classroom management, instructional strategies, and student engagement to the development of teachers' efficacy in physical education.

To ensure that instructional coaching programs are successful, there should not be a standardized definition of instructional coaching or a single model for school usage. School districts need to have the flexibility to identify the best coaching model for achieving their improvement goals. Once the district's goals have been identified, the school leaders must thoroughly design a coaching program with clearly defined roles and responsibilities for the coaches. School administrators need to support the coaching program and allow coaches to work with teachers in a non-evaluative manner. Instructional coaching should never be seen as a punishment or a way to fix the teacher (Hawk, 2020).

The current study's baseline assessment will contribute knowledge to school administrations on organizing effective instructional coaching that develops the Physical education teachers' efficacy. School leaders have a responsibility to encourage teachers to utilize coaching as a form of professional learning. School leaders must also realize that coaching programs may need to change over time.

A district that begins with a teacher-centered model may change to a student-centered model once the desired initiative has been successfully implemented by teachers. As new teachers are hired, a differentiated coaching model may need to be employed. If instructional coaching programs are designed well and viewed as personalized professional learning for all teachers, students will be the benefactors of the improved school system (Hawk & Nelson, 2024).

Conclusion

The study encompassed a diverse group of physical education teachers regarding age, gender, educational qualifications, teaching experience, marital status, income, and position. Planning instructional coaching plays a vital role in effectively implementing instructional coaching. Additionally, observations and feedback are well-implemented and supported by school leaders.

Teachers effectively apply assessment and feedback strategies in their teaching-learning process but there is room for further improvement. Classroom management is identified as an area of importance emphasizing the need for professional development to address challenges associated with disruptive behaviors. Teachers employ impactful instructional strategies yet improvements to better cater to students' needs could be explored. Student engagement is generally well-implemented although more strategic planning may

be needed to encourage active participation.

This study's foundation, the above-mentioned Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS), ensures that all teachers focus on their job hard work to accomplish the DepEd's vision, mission, values, and strategic priorities. To uphold the agency's administrative directive, vision, and mission, DepEd endeavors to reinforce the principles of responsibility and performance toward the department's success in the implementation of professional growth inside the school. Monitoring individual performance and how it tells to complete objectives requires the use of a dimension system. Coaching and mentoring are highly suggested to develop all the strategies and techniques that some teachers need.

Female teachers report higher efficacy in various teaching dimensions, suggesting that gender may influence how teachers perceive their effectiveness in the classroom. Teachers with higher monthly incomes tend to report lower efficacy, particularly in classroom management. Teachers in higher positions also reported lower efficacy across various teaching dimensions. Thus, certain demographic characteristics can impact a teacher's self-efficacy in their teaching roles.

According to Bandura's further explanation, those who visualize successful outcomes have a strong sense of efficacy. A strong feeling of self-efficacy uplifts the spirit and encourages personal achievement. Conversely, individuals who were uncertain about their effectiveness considered worst-case scenarios and focused on the things they believed would spiral out of control. That is, people decide to take action based on their perception of their abilities.

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